

To the Clerk to the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

Memorandum in response to the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021, submitted by the undersigned

We are a nation proud of our motto freedom and justice, and yet we are attempting to restrict the freedom of and deny justice to a targeted group of fellow citizens. We claim to value our independence and yet we are allowing foreign organisations to shape our nation's moral landscape, with likely far-reaching and detrimental consequences. The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 claims the moral high ground and yet proposes the most un-Christ-like behaviour.

The proposed bill claims to ensure the safety of our children, and yet it quite deliberately endangers the physical and emotional welfare of a group of our young most in need of our understanding, protection, and support. The bill denies them the right to seek the emotional support of their choosing, instead advocating conversion therapy, a practice known to cause psychological distress and harm. The bill specifically includes individuals who are intersex, proposing 'approved service providers' to 'assist the parent realign the child to the appropriate binary designation as determined by a medical practitioner'. It denies the child any voice in deciding what is appropriate – a denial of their human rights.

Section 13 of The Children's Act 1998

No person shall subject a child to torture or other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment including any cultural practice which dehumanises or is injurious to the physical and mental well-being of a child.

At the time that they reach legal majority, the bill denies a targeted group of our Citizens, the right to live their lives in peace and privacy, to plan for their futures, to make financial provision for their partners in sickness and at the time of their death.

Article 12 of the 1992 Constitution of Ghana

Every person in Ghana, whatever his race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender shall be entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individual contained in this Chapter but subject to respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for the public interest.

As if this were not bad enough, the bill denies them the right to legal representation and seeks to ban outright any form of social or legal advocacy in their support and defence.

Article 19 of the 1992 Ghana Constitution

A person charged with a criminal offence shall be permitted to defend himself before the court or by a lawyer of his choice.

The Children's Act 1998 guarantees the protection of children from inhuman or degrading treatment.

The 1992 Constitution of Ghana

- 1) guarantees the protection of the fundamental human rights of every person in Ghana, subject to the rights and freedoms of others and the public interest (Article 12);
- 2) guarantees the right to life of all persons (Article 13);

- 3) acknowledges the right to personal liberty (Article 14);
- 4) provides that the dignity of all persons shall be inviolable (Article 15);
- 5) provides that any person charged with a criminal offence shall be given a fair hearing within a reasonable time by a court (Article 19)
- 6) highlights the freedom of association (Article 21)

This bill aims to deliberately exclude a group of persons from the constitutional rights guaranteed to all others, to silence any call for justice they may attempt, and to criminalize their very existence.

The hate-filled and divisive nature of the bill encourages neighbour to report on neighbour, a deeply abhorrent practice, and actively encourages further persecution of individuals who already face violence and persecution. We as a nation are better than this.

I urge all Members of Parliament to reject this proposed Bill outright and to uphold their duty to protect all citizens of Ghana equally.

30 September 2021

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